

Microbiomes4Soy Website

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MICROBIOMES4SOY

Full name

Healthier diets and sustainable food and feed systems through employing microbiomes for soya production and further use

Project URL

www.microbiomes4soy.eu

EU project officer

Celine Dondeynaz

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Executive summary

This deliverable outlines the development and structure of the MICROBIOMES4SOY project website, which serves as the primary information hub for stakeholders. Coordinated by EUFIC (European Food Information Council), the website aims to inform audiences about the project's objectives, activities, partners, publications, news, events, and results. It will be seamlessly integrated with the project's other media channels, including the project LinkedIn account, the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) and EUFIC's SciFoodHealth social media feeds on LinkedIn and X (Twitter) under the hashtag #MICROBIOMES4SOY.

Website Creation Process

As a first step, after consulting the project coordination team, EUFIC defined the first structure for the website, intending to collect quotes from potential suppliers. In January 2024, 3 quotes were requested for web developer companies and a final one was chosen considering the economic and technical offer. The homepage of the website was launched on the 2nd of May 2024, and the full website will be developed by the end of June 2024, using the domain <https://microbiomes4soy.eu/> purchased by EUFIC. The domain <https://www.microbiome4soy.eu> (without the "s" at the end of microbiomes) was also purchased to redirect users in case of a spelling error.

Technical Details

The MICROBIOMES4SOY website will utilize WordPress as its Content Management System (CMS), hosted on EUFIC's own OVH servers which are based in the EU (France). EUFIC will retain copyrights, with technical support provided until January 2029 and maintenance continuing for three years post-project to ensure security and usability. Developed by the web designers, WordPress was

chosen for its open-source nature, with EUFIC owning copyrights. Technical support will be available until January 2029, with maintenance extending until December 2031, including updates, security monitoring, and Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate maintenance for uninterrupted browsing.

The website content will be prepared with the contribution of all project partners, but EUFIC will be responsible for fine-tuning the texts provided and for uploading content on the website. The website will be built with an end-user perspective to raise the interest of our main target audiences.

Website Overview

The MICROBIOMES4SOY project's website is the central hub for disseminating information about the project to all potential stakeholders. Coordinated by EUFIC, the website creation process ensures alignment with the project's visual identity and meets the needs and requirements of WP leaders. It serves as the primary source of information, offering comprehensive details on scopes, activities, partners, publications, news, events, and results. By connecting to various platforms, including social media and scientific publications, the website enhances accessibility to project updates and resources for stakeholders.

The website will undergo regular updates, featuring project updates, lay articles/blog posts on relevant topics, upcoming events, public deliverables, scientific publications, and other communication materials, including visual graphics.

The project website will include the following sections:

1. **Homepage:** The initial point of entry featuring up-to-date news items about the project, the project objective's introduction, and a sign-up link for the project newsletter.
2. **About Page:** Will provide fundamental project details and profiles of consortium members and the Scientific Advisory Board.

3. **News, Press, and Events Page:** Highlights project updates, press features, and upcoming events.
4. **Resources Page:** Contains project results, documents, publications, and informative materials.
5. **Contact Page:** Provides contact information and links to social media platforms and the project hashtag.
6. **Articles:** Hosts articles related to project topics to keep stakeholders informed.

The website provides convenient access to the project's social media channels for regular updates and insights. Furthermore, the website includes a dedicated privacy policy page to ensure transparency regarding data handling and protection measures.

Below are screenshots provided from the homepage of the website.

MICROBIOMES4SOY

Microbiomes for Sustainable Food Systems: Paving the Pathway to Transition

Microbiomes4Soy will foster the transition to better planetary health through:

- 1 Developing microbiome-based knowledge and awareness
- 2 Creating microbiome-based solutions for more sustainable food production
- 3 Facilitating healthy soy-enriched diets.

MICROBIOMES4SOY: Healthier diets and sustainable food and feed systems through employing microbiomes for soya production and further use

What is MICROBIOMES4SOY?

MICROBIOMES4SOY is a 5-year research project funded by the European Commission through the Horizon Europe program. Coordinated by the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT), the project gathers 17 partners from 10 countries in a collaboration between top universities and research centres, as well as expert non-profit organizations and the private sector.

 The project aims to improve the environmental impact of soybean production, explore the effects of soybean consumption on the human gut microbiome and contribute to the development of novel fish feeds for the aquaculture sector. Through a Multi-Actor Approach, the project will develop transition pathways that are ready to answer food system actors' needs and deliver co-benefits relevant to the FOOD 2030 priorities.

Partners

Meet Our Project Partners

The MICROBIOMES4SOY project is coordinated by the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT) and involves 18 partners from 10 countries, including top universities, research centers, non-profit organizations, and the private sector.

[Stay updated →](#)

Microbiomes4Soy Newsletter

Don't miss any updates, subscribe to the project newsletter

Your email address

I agree to receive the MICROBIOMES4SOY newsletter and I have read and accepted the [privacy policy](#).

Supportive Materials

The project is supported by an active, modern visual identity implemented in the logo and brand guidelines.

Website Development Process

The development process involved collaboration with the web developers and the project partners to ensure the website effectively communicated the project's message and engaged target audiences.

Conclusion

The MICROBIOMES4SOY project website stands as a pivotal platform for engaging stakeholders and disseminating significant information about the project's objectives, activities, and outcomes. The website integrates the graphic

identity of MICROBIOMES4SOY brand. Different graphic materials will link to the website, which can be used for different events and purposes, and are supportive of raising awareness about the project.

With a user-friendly interface and comprehensive sections covering various aspects of the project, the website serves as an entry point for all stakeholders, providing them with easy access to essential resources. From the homepage, which offers a glimpse into project updates and events, to the About page detailing the project's vision and partners, each section plays a crucial role in fostering understanding and engagement.

Furthermore, the inclusion of dedicated sections for news, press, and events ensures that stakeholders are kept informed about the project's progress and upcoming activities. The integration of social media links and a privacy policy page further enhances transparency and connectivity, allowing stakeholders to stay connected and informed. Overall, the MICROBIOMES4SOY website serves as a comprehensive information hub, facilitating collaboration and awareness to drive the Project towards its objectives.

Contact and details

Coordinator

Organization AIT Austrian Institute of Technology

Abbreviation AIT

Work Package 6 leader

Organization European Food Information Council

Abbreviation

EUFIC